

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INNOVATIVE IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article focuses on the use of moisture-retaining hydrogel as a water-saving technology for winter wheat. In addition, information about moisture-retaining hydrogel is provided, that is, about the areas of its advantage.

Key words: Winter wheat, water, hydrogel, melioration, irrigation, technology, resource, yield, cultivation, biological, grain, norm, soil, grain.

Currently, 2.1 billion tons of grain are grown worldwide, of which wheat grain makes up 759.6 million tons of the gross harvest. The wheat cultivation area is 243.5 million hectares, including countries such as USA, Germany, China, India, Brazil, Australia, Canada, Russia, and Ukraine grow wheat on the basis of modern technologies. Scientists say that by 2050, grain production in the world is expected to reach 3 billion tons.

The application of modern agro-technologies in the cultivation of winter wheat varieties, the effective use of irrigated land along with the increase in grain yield, and the improvement of technological quality indicators of grain are gaining great importance today. In irrigated conditions, each province has its own soil and climate conditions, depending on its geographical location and regions.

The Bukhara oasis differs from other regions of Uzbekistan due to its soil and climate conditions. Cultivation of promising varieties of winter wheat in the conditions of saline and salinity-prone soils of the Bukhara region, cultivation of winter wheat varieties taking into account their biological characteristics,

preparation of land and seeds for sowing, method of sowing, rate, terms, scientific research on application and further improvement of feeding with organic and mineral fertilizers, watering procedures, periods, effective methods of fighting against weeds, diseases and pests, as well as the use of resource-saving technologies remains relevant to this day.

To date, there are a number of water-saving irrigation methods, especially in the cultivation of autumn grain crops, mainly sprinkler irrigation or a number of improved methods of surface irrigation are used. In the conditions of the Bukhara region, till now, irrigation works are carried out mainly through traditional irrigation in irrigated agriculture. At the same time, due to the conditions created in our republic, modern irrigation methods are used today. To date, a lot of research is being conducted by scientists of the world to increase the productivity of agricultural crops and at the same time use resource-saving technologies in irrigated agriculture. In recent years, a lot of research has been conducted not only on irrigation of irrigated fields, but also on maintaining soil moisture in cultivated fields. We also conducted a series of experiments on obtaining a high yield of winter wheat while maintaining soil moisture. In these experiments, we used a moisture-retaining hydrogel as a moisture-retaining technology. Our experiment was conducted mainly in relation to the control option, that is, in the control option, the moisture-retaining hydrogel was not used, and in the other options, it was used in different amounts. The advantage of moisture-retaining hydrogel is that no additional devices and equipment are required in the irrigated area, we only need to add moisture-retaining hydrogel to the soil, and we can also carry out irrigation in the traditional way, while saving water resources and improving the condition of the soil. We also improve it, that is, after the moisture-retaining hydrogel has done its job, it turns into soil humus and enriches the soil composition. In addition, if the irrigated land where the hydrogel is applied is saline or prone to salinity, it prevents and reduces soil salinity by retaining moisture in the soil. Unfortunately, most farmers do not have complete information about moisture-retaining hydrogel and its useful properties. Its main

advantage is that hydrogel saves time and water during irrigation. Also, we believe that saving money spent on mineral fertilizers is one of its priority aspects. Brief information about moisture-retaining hydrogel: Moisture-retaining hydrogel is a synthetic polymer with moisture-absorbing, high-swelling properties, and is strong in macro- and micronutrients necessary for plants, as well as in the development of crops. has effecting microorganisms. It provides the opportunity to store a large amount of moisture in the soil for a long time and reabsorb unabsorbed mineral fertilizers for the plant.

According to a number of cited data, moisture-retaining hydrogel has the ability to absorb 200-300 times its own weight in rainwater, and 200-250 times more water in soils, depending on the amount of different salts in the soil. Water that has passed to the soil through atmospheric precipitation or irrigation is stored in a state where it can easily pass to the roots of plants. The advantages of using hydrogels: can save irrigation water by 20-40%, reduce the consumption of mineral fertilizers due to retention in the fertile layer of the soil, enrich the fertile layer and increase productivity, protect the lands and groundwater from salinity preserves, increases the yield of agricultural crops and has other advantages. It should be noted that hydrogel does not lose its properties even if it is used for 3-4 years. Products formed from the destruction of old hydrogel do not destroy the earth's infrastructure. On the contrary, as a nitrogenous fertilizer, it is easy for plants to assimilate. During the experiments conducted by scientists, it was determined that the decomposition process of hydrogels is completely harmless.

In conclusion, it can be said that today there are different types of moisture-retaining hydrogels in the world, and the main function of moisture-retaining hydrogels is to save water resources. In addition to saving water, the main achievement of moisture-retaining hydrogel is the presence of organic compounds and various biological organisms. When we used water-retaining hydrogel in the soil for winter wheat cultivation, good results were recorded in terms of plant growth and development, as well as saving water resources. and the yield was higher

compared to the control variant. The condition of soil reclamation has improved in the variants using moisture-retaining hydrogel. It should be noted that various innovative technologies are emerging in agriculture every day, and if we study and apply these technologies, this is certainly our achievement.

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